

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF SPEECH FORMATION IN BLIND CHILDREN

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Annotation. The peculiarities of the logopedic work carried out with blind children due to a violation of the activity of the visual analyzer, the speech development of blind and weak-sighted children has its own characteristics, which are reflected in speech (echolalia, "formalism", violation of the word category, etc.). This article describes such information as working with Blind Children, methods of teaching them, the role of educators in solving their problems in speech development.

Keywords: Blind Children, speech therapy, weak-sighted children, expressive speech, tiflopedagog.

The existing research in the speech therapy is mainly devoted to the defects in the pronunciation of children with a deep impairment in vision (M. Ye. Khvatsev, S.L.Shapiro, A.D.Shipilo, S.V.Yakhontova). only in the 60-70s with the development of a systematic study of speech deficiencies in speech in speech therapy (R. Ye.Levina, V.K.Orfinskaya) research has appeared on the identification of shortcomings in the speech of blind and weak-sighted children not only in the pronunciation of sounds, but also in the development of speech. This is the work of specialists and logopedists in the methodology of teaching the native language (O.L.Zhilsova, S.L.Korobko, N.S.Kostyuchyak, N.A.Krylova, T.P.Sviridyuk). For Example, S.L.Korobko's speech divided the adult group of full, underdeveloped vulnerable children.

In the present time, the correlation of speech deficit in blind and weak-sighted children is a complex defect and the lack of speech and visual activity has been proven in theoretical and practical research.

Speech deficiencies of children with a visual impairment are typical. They are complex in structure and level quality, covering speech, as R. Ye.Levina noted, as a single system, and in this, speech defects do not remain the only core of speech defects. The development of speech in such children takes place in complex conditions. Among them, congenital forms of visual anomalies occur, and this condition also causes disorders of other functions related to the appearance of speech.

Statistical materials show that speech impairments are more common in children who have profound visual impairments compared to children who see.

The fact that the research carried out has formed the speech of children in this category allows you to divide it into four levels.

First level. It is expressed in the presence of some shortcomings in pronunciation.

Second level. Active vocabulary is limited. When comparing the image of the word and pedmet, mistakes are made when drawing up stories of generalizing concepts. Defects in pronunciation are manifested in lambdasism, parasigmatism, pararotatism, paralambdasism in various manifestations of sigmatism. Vowel pronunciations and phonematic

representations are observed to be deficient in the development of auditory differson. Phonemic analysis will not be formed.

Third level. Expressive speech is characterized by a sluggish vocabulary. The level of knowledge of generalizing concepts, comparison of the image of the word and the subject will be low. The grammatical side of independent speech is distorted, it will consist only of naming objects and one two-word sentence. Complex storytelling will be underdeveloped, pronunciation and auditory differentiation will be formed sluggishly.

Fourth level. Expressive speech is very limited, there will be serious shortcomings in the comparison of generalizing concepts and the image of the word-object. Connected speech consists of some words, exolalia are observed. Tasks aimed at determining the grammatical structure of speech and tasks related to auditory differentiation cannot be performed. There is a general underdevelopment of phonemic analysis and synthesis.

Analysis of the development of speech in children with visual impairment shows that in many of them systemic defects are observed, and the adequate components of speech are distorted (phonetics, lexicon, grammar). We observe their similarity if we compare defects in the speech of children with Normal vision and visual impairment. Alternatively, the notation also has a large difference in terms of the degree of defects and factors of formation. As a result of the deficiency (lack) of subject images, difficulties in grammatically correct construction of complex sentences and sentences are observed in speech memory. General and private factors have been identified as a result of the first natal and postnatal pathological changes in Anamnesis, which cause impaired vision to underdevelopment of children's speech and significantly retard the development of a number of functions that affect the formation of their speech (Praxis, Gnosis, coordination, chamization). Hence, in the early postnatal period, a congenital or early acquired visual defect remains a primary defect that affects the development of non-specific functions. In children with Visual Impairment, There are many deficiencies that limit movement activity and cause them to be unable to establish contact with the surrounding world. In the development of psychic processes (including speech), the quality of speech communication, the micro-social environment has a huge impact.

Thus, the polemorphism of the factors that cause systemic speech disorders that cover one or another speech component causes a more complex defect to appear.

Congenital or premature acquired visual impairment is the main cause of speech underdevelopment, and the effect may increase or lose strength, depending on the presence of other pathological factors.

The study of speech deficiencies of blind and weak-sighted children requires the accounting and analysis of not only all components of speech, but also most non-specific functions. This constitutes a comprehensive logopedic verification methodology. The peculiarity of the complex verification methodology is that the study of speech defects in these children and the factors that cause them is carried out in the case when the visual perception, methods of reception and the resulting methods of transmitting materials. Most children with a deep impairment in such vision will have to take into account the fact that the game activity has no qualifications and their knowledge of the world of objects is limited. For this reason, before completing tasks during the examination, the child is given specific constructions, demonstratives, examples of joint fulfillment.

The main focus should be on the state of expressive speech. Correctional work with blind and weak-sighted preschool and school-age children is carried out in a natural

pedagogical process. It is organized in a leading didactic and special principles taking into account.

Special principles include correctional education, taking into account primary and secondary defects, relying on existing analyzers and forming (dressing) a polysensory basis, forming comprehensive concepts in the world around us, specifying the level of speech formation, relying on the preserved components of speech activity, predicting the novelty of verbal material, the complexity of its material. In the process of correctional education, a comprehensive effect is shown. This effect is achieved by speech therapist, teacher (in school), tiflopedagog (in kindergarten) and educators during various activities.

In correctional work, the logopedic effect is given a very high degree of relevance. This effect is carried out in specially organized training. Training is carried out on a scale that takes into account the vision, speech, methods of admission and individual characteristics of children. Depending on the Shung is organized logopedic gurus. Classes are conducted individually for a long time, taking into account the peculiarity of the difficulties in working with Blind Children. In combination with a complex speech deficit, non-verbal functions are not formed, that is, with children with a turtleneck speech level, Ham is more individual training.

The educator and tiflopedagogos (school teachers), together with the speech therapist, determine the tasks of eliminating speech defects. Correctional and logopedic tasks in the development of speech culture are carried out in Game, educational and labor activities, as well as practical and musical training.

In organizing speech therapy sessions with weak-sighted children, the main emphasis is on the possibility of using the preserved visual activity (didactic material of the required size, color), relief drawings, "wonderful bags", cubes and pencils (for marking sound, steam and sentences).

Natural visual weapons are of great importance in shaping the perception of the world of objects about ken inclusiveness. Training is necessarily carried out through play, the reason is that in children with a deep visual impairment, play activity is formed too late.

When planning a correctional-logopedic work with children in which it is determined that **the first level** of speech has developed, a good speech base of these children is taken into account, the main focus is on the development of the phonetic side of speech, games and exercises are given that develop auditory attention. Due to the difficulty of mimicking blind Bos, sounds are placed on them by mechanical means.

All sections of the work carried out with the children of **the primary group** are preserved and taken into account when planning the logopedic effect to be carried out with children, in which secondary speech is found to have developed. But the focus here is on increasing vocabulary, developing phonemic analysis and synthesis.

When dealing with **third-and fourth-level** Bos, logopedes (in agreement with tiflopedagog and educators) introduce elements aimed at correcting education and play, practical activities. This should include motor skills, chambering and clairvoyance skills. This work inextricably links the development of speech skills and the formation of relevant concepts. On the basis of this, the formation of deep concepts and knowledge about the universe around us in children lies. Taking into account the characteristics of blind and weak-sighted children in this group, the main focus is on increasing the wealth of vocabulary in

them, correctly comparing the word with the image of the subject, developing generalizing concepts, a grammatical system and independent speech.

On the basis of this work lies the formation and enrichment of speech stereotypes. The enrichment of the vocabulary, the practical application of the grammatical system makes it possible for the process of composing sentences on pictures (relief drawings for the blind). In speech training, children are treated on weak vapors in speech activity. The cooperation of a speech therapist, educator, tiflopedagog (teacher) creates the speech base necessary for school education. On the basis of formed speech, speech speech speech speech can go to the upbringing of the skills of speech automation and the teaching of phonemic analysis and synthesis (with children of levels 3 and 4).

The base of speech and objects, formed by the educator and tiflopedagog, is widely used and improved in speech and speech speech speech. Also, the work of the educator and tiflopedagog will be continued in training. Their work is planned on an inextricable basis (games aimed at strengthening the skills of correct pronunciation and material for strengthening the skills of speech, vocabulary and bound speech).

In general, we can also talk about the logopedization of the pedagogical process. In elementary grades, the teacher is carried out in the inextricable connection of the educator's work in teaching literacy and the development of speech. The teacher will strengthen the speech-skills acquired in speech-skills in speech-speech training. Such work (complex, correctional and methodological) requires the speech therapist to know not only high qualifications, but also children with deep visual impairments, their characteristics and organization of activities, a special school program.

Rhinolalia, stuttering, sound defects are eliminated in speech defects in blind and weak-sighted children in speech therapy. The work is carried out taking into account their general methods, relying on preserved vision or special methods (in Blind Children).

The problem of speech impairment, which occurs in children with impaired mental development, is considered in the process of ontogenesis in terms of the interdependence of speech and thinking, the relationship of the child's cognitive activity and the processes of speech development. L.S. Vigotsky, J. Pije, A. Volonna, A.N. Leontyev, A.R. In his studies, Luria clearly outlined the main factors of the connection of speech and thinking. Vigotsky believes that the word is a combination of content and sounds, it has all the features of colloquial thinking. Also, L.S. Vigotsky argues that the contents manifest themselves at the same time as "speech as a host and as a host within the scope of thought... it is simultaneously Ham speech, Ham thinking, because it is the unity of speech risk". The development of speech and thinking in ontogenesis is plausible, L.S. Vigotsky comes to the following conclusion, the development of speech and thinking is carried out on uneven and non-parallel points, and they have absolutely dissimilar genetic bases.

The development of intellect in the course of speech development can be distinguished between the pre-speech phase and the pre-intellectual phase in speech development. At the first stage of development of the child's speech, various foundations of speech and thinking are observed. First, intellectual reactions are characteristic until the beginning of speech formation. Secondly, up to intellectual development, speech signs are observed.

Thus, the development of speech and thinking is carried out independently of each other until a certain vaccine. By the second year of the child khayotinig, the development of speech and thinking coincide. It is from this period that speech performs an intellectual

function. L.S. Vigotsky believes that the development of nutk depends on the socio-cultural experience of the child and the means of contemplation.

J.Piaje reveals the cognitive (intellectual) basis of speech development. He believes that the development of sensomatous intelect plays a role in the development of nutk in a child.

The development of sensomatous intelect is carried out in several clicks. The first boskich is a sensomotor Mantic boskich. In this, the child directly studies the logic of the behavior of the perceived objects. Later, the child moves from the logic of character to "conceptual" logic, which is based on imagination and thinking. In this, what is not directly perceived – the skills of thinking are formed in the khadisas khaki. This boskich is suitable for two years of age of the child. J. Piajé believes that language is formed on the basis of semiotic (symbolic) functions and is his personal phenomenon.

J. Piaje concludes that language is formed on the basis of thought, language is a personal State of symbolic function, and is formed by a certain period of Child Development. Thus, speech proves to occur at a given cognitive /intellectual/ base. In the later stages of the child's development, the relationship of speech and thinking can be considered in different aspects. In this case, the problem arises of how the intellectual development of the child affects the development of the speech process. In halting this problem, it is possible to indicate 3 basic plans of the songnetiv criterion of speech development.

1. The level of intellectual development of the child is reflected at the semantic level, which forms the basis of speech. The child narrates the UZ tasavurs in tevarak-around khaki through speech. When a child does not understand this or that language form, he cannot use this language form. Therefore, children first assimilate simple language forms, corresponding to his intellectual level, able to reflect, with a semantic point of view. The speech of the child uses first the words denoting the place, and later the words denoting the concept of time.

2. The degree of non-formation of the child's thinking activity negatively affects the acquisition of formal language tools. In the process of ontogenesis, the child not only imitates the speech of those around him, but also takes over the language laws that form the basis of speech. To master the laws of language, it is imperative that the child's taxing, descriptive, generalizing and defferencing processes are formed.

3. In the case of a short memory charge, the possession of speech in the Hall associated with the possibility of revising information. Human speech is expressed and perceived in a short time. The occupation of speech from the side of the child will depend on the possibilities of re-apprehension of speech information.

References:

- 1.Jalilovna, Q. N., Rustamjon o'gli, Y. D., Xosiljon o'g'li, M. J., & Isroiljonovich, I. O. (2021, January). HIMOYA GAZLARI MUHITIDA PAYVANDLASHDA MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 47-48).
- 2.Кобулова, Н. Ж., & Нарзиев, Ш. М. (2021, December). ХОДИМЛАРНИНГ МЕХНАТИНИ МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ. In Здравствуйте, уважаемые участники международной научной и научно-технической конференции, дорогие гости (p. 485).

3. Кабулова, Н. Ж. (2020). Традиционно-национальный узбекский головной убор мужчин (тюбетейка-дуппи) ферганской долины. *Universum: технические науки*, (8-2 (77)), 10-12.
4. Qobulova, N. J., Abdumutalibov, J., & Akbarov, A. (2022). ISHLAB CHIQARISH KORXONASIDA MEHNAT XAVFSIZLIGINI BOSHQARISH TIZIMI (MXBT) NI TAHLILI. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(6), 218-223.
5. Кабулова, Н. Д., Ходжакулов, М. Н., & Рахимов, Д. Б. (2021). АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОГРАММНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ (ПОИСКОВО-ИНФОРМАЦИОННАЯ КАРТОГРАФИЧЕСКАЯ СЛУЖБА, ГЕОЛОКАЦИЯ) В ПОДРАЗДЕЛЕНИЯХ МИНИСТЕРСТВА ПО ЧРЕЗВЫЧАЙНЫМ СИТУАЦИЯМ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. *Universum: технические науки*, (7-1 (88)), 14-17.
6. Халматов, М. М., Исмаилходжаев, Б. Ш., Кабулова, Н. Ж., & Хусанов, Д. Д. (2021). ГЕОФИЗИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ АТМОСФЕРНЫХ ЗАГРЯЗНИТЕЛЕЙ В АНДИЖАНЕ НА ОСНОВЕ УРАВНЕНИЙ АЭРОДИНАМИКИ. *Universum: химия и биология*, (6-1 (84)), 30-34.
7. Алимова, Х. А., Арипджанова, Д. У., Хайдаров, К. Б., & Кабулова, Н. Ж. (2013). Фрикционные свойства натурального шелка. *Ж. Композиционные материалы.-2013*, 2, 25-27.
8. Qobulova N.J., Abdurahmonov A., Musaev M., & Mahkmudov Sh. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SAFE TECHNOLOGY OF FUEL BRIQUETTES BASED ON FOOD AND AGRICULTURAL ORGANIC WASTE. *Экономика и социум*, (2-2 (93)), 312-315.
9. Muhammato'vich, H. M., & Muxtorjonc, X. (2022). ELIMINATION OF POLLUTIONS IN THE ATMOSPHERIC AIR'RGANISH. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 6, 43-47.
10. Halmatov, M. M., Ismayilkhodjaev, B. S., & Khamrakulov, A. G. (2019). GEOPHYSICAL MODELING OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF POLLUTANTS IN THE ATMOSPHERE OF ANDIJAN BASED ON THE AERODYNAMIC EQUATION. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(9), 70-77.
11. Халматов, М., Хожиматов, А., Хамракулов, А. Г., & Хусанов, Д. Д. (2018). РОЛЬ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ НАСАЖДЕНИЙ В УЛУЧШЕНИИ МИКРОКЛИМАТА АТМОСФЕРНОЙ СРЕДЫ. *Наука и мир*, 2(12), 20-23.
12. Халматов, М. М., Хожиматов, А., Содиков, К., & Солижонов, С. Э. (2017). ВЛИЯНИЕ АТМОСФЕРНОЙ ПОГОДЫ НА МИКРОКЛИМАТ ДЕРЕВЯННЫХ НАСАЖДЕНИЙ. In *Научно-практические пути повышения экологической устойчивости и социально-экономическое обеспечение сельскохозяйственного производства* (pp. 110-112).
13. Khalmatov, M., Khozhimatov, A., Khamrakulov, A. G., & Khusanov, D. D. (2013). THE ROLE OF GREEN SPACES IN IMPROVING THE MICROCLIMATE OF THE ATMOSPHERIC ENVIRONMENT. *SCIENCE AND WORLD*, 23.
14. Abdurakhmonov, A. A., & Dadabayeva, N. A. PREVENT SERIOUS INFECTIOUS DISEASES AND THEIR SPREAD PRECAUTIONARY MEASURES.
15. Abdurakhmonov, A. THE CONCEPT OF NATURE AND HEROES IN "ROCKS ALSO CRY". *EPR International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 1, 481.
16. Abdurashid, A. (2023). Efficient Method Of Biogas Production. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 17, 28-34.

- 17.Рахимов, А. Ю., Абдурахмонов, А. А., & Сулаймонов, Ш. А. (2015). Изучение состояния использования ваты-сдира и пути повышения качества коконного сырья. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (4), 152-157.
- 18.Jalilov, A., Нилуфар, К., & Xalmatov, M. (2023). WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFECTS OF HEAVY METALS IN THE ATMOSPHERE ON LANDSCAPE TREES AND SOILS.© ООО «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА».
- 19.Jalilov, A., & JALILOV, A. (2022). O'zbekiston respublikasi atrof-tabiiy muhit va ekologiyaning yomonlashuvi bilan bog'liq favqulodda vaziyatlarning oldini olish muammolari.
- 20.Jalilov, A. (2022). MODEL FOR IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMATIC ISSUES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF OFFICIALS OF THE NATIONAL CENTER FOR ACTION AND MANAGEMENT OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS OF THE MINISTRY OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
- 21.Jalilov, A., & JALILOV, A. (2022). Improving Ways to Raise Earthquake Sustainability of the Individual Buildings in Uzbekistan.
- 22.Jalilov, A. (2021). O'zbekistonda individual ravishda qurilgan binolarning zilzilabardoshligini oshirish yo'llarini takomillashtirish.
- 23.Ahmadbek, J. (2023). FAVQULODDA VA EKOLOGIK OFAT HOLATLARIDA KORXONA BOSHQARUVI. Involta Scientific Journal, 2(4), 122-130.
24. Нилуфар, К., Jalilov, A., & Xalmatov, M. (2023). «EFFECT OF HARMFUL SUBSTANCES IN THE ATMOSPHERE ON TREE COVER». © ООО «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА».
- 25.Jalilov, A. (2023). «LOYDAN TIKLANGAN DEVORLAR MUSTANKAMLIGINI O'RGANISH». © ООО «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА».
26. Jalilov, A. (2023). Enterprise Management in Emergency and Environmental Disaster Situations. Wwww. grnjournal.Us.
- 27.Жалилов, А. (2022). Модель для выявления и анализа проблемных вопросов в деятельности должностных лиц национального центра действий и управления чрезвычайными ситуациями министерства по чрезвычайным ситуациям. in Library, 22(4), 25-32.
28. Tursunov, X. T., & Rahimova, T. U. (2006). Ekologiya.
29. Khalmatov, M., Khozhimatov, A., Khamrakulov, A. G., & Khusanov, D. D. (2013). THE ROLE OF GREEN SPACES IN IMPROVING THE MICROCLIMATE OF THE ATMOSPHERIC ENVIRONMENT. SCIENCE AND WORLD, 23.
- 30.Nafasova, D. (2022). TABIIY RESURSLARNI BOSHQARISH, EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF-MUHIT MUHOFAZASI. Scientific progress, 3(3), 739-744.